

Synthesis and Characterization New 1, 2, 4-Triazole Derivative and Its Complexes with Some Transition Metal Ions

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Abstract:

An innovative class of ligand compounds using The ions of transition metals (Cr(III), Fe(III), and Ni(II)). The ligand N,N'-(4H-1,2,4-triazole-3,5-diyl)bis(4-methoxybenzamide) was produced by reacting 2,5-di amino-1,2,4-triazole with two moles of methyl 4-methoxybenzoate in the presence of ethanol and a few drops of glacial acetic acid. The recently produced chemicals were studied using a battery of analytical tools, analysis of elements (C, H, and N), nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, and atomic absorption are some of the techniques that are included. The aforementioned

diagnostic procedures led to the formation of ligand-containing octahedral complexes with (Fe and Cr) ions and a square planer complex with nickel.

Keywords: *Synthesis, Characterization, 1, 2, 4-Triazole, methyl 4-methoxybenzoate, magnetic susceptibility.*

Introduction

There has been a critical need to synthesize novel anti-infective chemicals for the purpose of treating illnesses caused by microorganisms due to the alarming global issue of multidrug-resistant germs in recent decades. Numerous medicinally significant compounds, most of which exhibit antibacterial properties, have the 1,2,4-triazole nucleus (Patel, & Parmar, 2010). The broad variety of biological activity shown by organic molecules containing heterocyclic ring structures keeps them in high demand. The structural properties of many bioactive compounds include heterocyclic systems, Examples of such compounds are 1, 2, 4-triazoles, 1, 3, 4-thiadiazoles, and derivatives of these compounds. These molecules have acquired relevance (Naeimi, Safari, & Heidarneshad, 2007). It is well-known that several medications have triazole and thiadiazole rings in their structures (Lippard, & Berg, 1994).

Novel compounds derived from 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles and 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiones which are heterocyclic compounds, have garnered a lot of interest due to their many desirable biological characteristics, including antibacterial and antifungal effects Mohammad, & Shoukry, (2001) and Sallomi, & Shaheen, (1998), respectively. Anticonvulsant, anti-inflammatory, antitumoral, antioxidant, antitubercular, antiviral, and so on. These findings need further investigation into biological properties of compounds comprising 1, 2, 4-triazole and 1, 3, 4-thiadiazole have been investigated.

Material and Methods

Fluka and B.D.H. Chemicals were the companies that provided the chemicals to the company. The infrared spectra were obtained using a Shimadzu FT-IR-spectrometer device with KBr discs for the generated ligands and CsI

discs for the metal ion complexes. Element analyses were carried out on a Thermofinigan flash. Our flame spectrophotometer—a Shimadzu A-A-500 AFG from Japan with the serial number 23-0932-21-0015 and the following specifications: power-150, voltage-AC110/220V, 50-60 Hz—allowed us to determine the relative amounts of the transition metals in the artificial complexes. ¹H NMR spectra at 500 MHz were captured using the Bruker DRX System AL. At an energy of 70 eV, the HP/MS Model 5973 Network Mass Selective Detector was used in order to record the mass spectra of both the ligand and the complexes. Using the Gouy technique and the Balance Magnetic Susceptibility Model (MSB Auto), magnetic measurements were taken. At room temperature, the complexes' molar conductance in DMSO was measured using an Inolabcond 720 conductivity meter.

Preparation of the Ligand (L)

To begin the ligand synthesis, 50 ml of ethanol and a few drops of glacial acetic acid were combined with 3.32 g of methyl 4-methoxybenzoate, which had a molecular weight of 0.02 mol. Then, this alcoholic solution was supplemented containing 0.99 g of 3, 5-diamino-1, 2, 4-triazole and 0.01 mol of thiazole. Eight hours of refluxing heat was applied to the reaction mixture. Thanks to TLC, we know the response is complete. After the solvent was largely evaporated at decreasing pressure using a rotary evaporator, For the purpose of obtaining the pure chemical, the product was recrystallized from ethanol and water. With a melting point of (189-190) °C, a physical appearance of yellow crystals, and a yield percentage of 89%.

Figure 1. Preparation of the Ligand

A General Approach to Ligand Complex Preparation

The reaction mixture consisted of four millimoles of ligand dissolved in sixty milliliters of absolute ethanol and four millimoles of

transition metal salt (CrCl₃·6H₂O FeCl₃, and the dissolution of NiCl₂·6H₂O in fifty milliliters of heated absolute ethanol. For three hours, the mixture was refluxed. Vacuum evaporation was used to remove the solvent once it cooled. A solution of DMF and ethanol (25-75 v/v) was

used to crystallize the precipitate after filtering (Patil, et al, 2011). The complexes that were

produced are listed in Table 1 along with their physical characteristics and molecular formulas.

Table 1. Displays the Physical Characteristics and Molecular Formula of the Resulting Complexes

No.	Formula	M.Wt	Color	(λ_{m}) ^a	M.P. °C	Yield%	μ_{eff}
1	Ligand	367	Yellow	-----	189-190	89.0	-----
2	[Cr(L) Cl ₂]Cl	529	green	81	206-208	72.2	3.6
3	[Fe(L) Cl ₂]Cl	525	Black	77	219-221	75.7	2.4
4	[Ni(L) Cl ₂]	495	Green	32	201-203	85.1	0.2

Note: a = $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (in DMSO solvent).

Results and Discussion

At room temperature, the solid states of the newly synthesized ligands and their complexes exhibit remarkable stability. While most organic solvents won't dissolve the ligands on their own, DMF and DMSO will dissolve the metal complexes they form.

Molar Conductance

The complexes' concentrations in 10⁻³ M DMSO solutions were measured in micrograms. Table 1 displays the values of the molar conductance. It follows that one-chloride ions are present outside the coordination sphere, owing to the fact that the results for Cr (III) and Fe (III) complexes indicate that these complexes are electrolytes with a ratio of 1:1. However, the values of the molar conductance (m) are not adequate to indicate the existence of an ionic molecule, thereby ruling out the possibility of an ionic complex; hence, the neutrality of the Ni (II) complex is established.

Magnetic Moments

The magnetic moments (μ_{eff}) of the complexes are shown in Table 1, which has the exact values after they include additional ligands. Complex 1 of iron(III) has a magnetic moment of 2.4 BM, which equates to one unpaired electron (Baluja, Solanki, & Kachhadia, 2006), and its low spin state is likely due to its spin-free octahedral shape. A low spin square planar configuration is based on the magnetic moment of the Ni(II) complex, which is 0.2 BM. With a magnetic moment of 3.6 BM, the Cr(III) complex likely

has a spin-free octahedral structure and three unpaired electrons.

IR Spectra

The generated coordination complexes were identified using the infrared spectra approach. The location of the donor atoms was determined by comparing the spectra with those of the free ligands. The several active groups, including (N-C=O), (C=O), (C=N endocyclic), (NH-endocyclic), (M-N), (M-O), and (M-Cl), were located using the infrared spectra, which also used to identify the ligand. The (N-C=O), (C=O), and (C=N endocyclic) groups are each represented by one of four bands seen in Ligand at (1622) cm⁻¹, (1665) cm⁻¹, and (1573) cm⁻¹, respectively. Furthermore, the presence of bands at (3134) cm⁻¹ and (3211) cm⁻¹ suggests the production of (C-H aromatic) and (NH endocyclic) bands, respectively. In metal complexes of ligands, certain frequencies that are stretching of the (C=N), (N-C=O), and (NH endocyclic) groups are reduced and transferred to reduced frequency ranges of roughly (12-45) cm⁻¹. This occurs because the ligands are attached to the metal, whereas the stretching frequencies of the (CH aromatic) and (C=O) groups are also diminished but do not change (Anatheil, Gatea, & Abdulredha, 2024); This is because these groups are unable to coordinate with metal ions, which is the reason why, this is the result. The areas (515-540) cm⁻¹, (552-586) cm⁻¹, and (210-308) cm⁻¹ show new bands that indicate coordination as (M-N), (M-O), and (M-Cl), respectively (Anatheil, Gatea, & Neamah, 2024). It can be seen in Figures 1 and Table 2

that the nitrogen and oxygen atoms that are present in the ligand's (C=N) and (C=O) groups have collaborated

Table 3. FT-IR Spectra of Ligand and Complexes

Compound	N-C=O	C=O	C=N endocyclic	NH endocyclic	C-H aromatic	M-N	M-O	M-Cl
ligand	1622	1665	1573	3211	3134	-----	-----	----
Cr-L	1606	1666	1566	3198	3134	524	578	210
Fe-L	1608	1665	1528	3178	3133	539	567	287
Ni-L	1614	1665	1564	3169	3134	522	552	308

1H NMR Spectra

At 9.9 ppm, the ligand's distinctive signals from the (-NH-endocyclic) proton are seen in the 1H NMR spectrum. Furthermore, two protons belonging to the (-NH) groups for the ligand may be responsible for the development of the band at 6.8 ppm. Both the ligand and aromatic ring protons may be represented by the band at 3.5 ppm, while the band at 7.5-8.4 ppm might be

the other possible candidate (Sekerci, & Tas, 2000).

Mass Spectra

Mass spectra of ligand

The scheme (1) incorporates an occurrence of the molecular ion peak, denoted by the symbol M+, the base peak, and a succession of peaks into the ligands' spectra (table 3).

Figure 2. Important Peaks of Mass Spectrum for Ligand

Table 3. Significant Peaks in the Ligand Mass Spectrum

No.	Fragmentation	m/z
1	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄ (Molecular ion)	367
2	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₅ O ₂	232
3	C ₁₀ H ₉ N ₄ O ₂	217
4	C ₇ H ₈ O	107
5	C ₂ H ₃ N ₅	97
6	C ₆ H ₇ O	96
7	C ₂ H ₂ N ₄	82
8	C ₆ H ₅ (base peak)	77
9	C ₂ H ₂ N ₃	68

Mass Spectra of Cr-L

The peak of the molecular ion (M⁺), base peak, and other significant peaks in the Cr-L spectrum are indicative of lost chloride atoms, which are incorporated in the break up (table 4).

Table 4. Significant Cr-L Peaks in the Mass Spectrum

No.	Fragmentation	m/z
1	[Cr(L) Cl ₂] ⁺ .Cl	525
2	[Cr(L) Cl ₂] ⁺ .	489
3	[Cr(L) Cl] ⁺ .	454
4	[Cr(L)] ⁺ .	418

Mass Spectra of Fe-L

The peak of the molecular ion [M⁺], base peak, and other significant peaks in the Fe-L spectrum

Table 7. Component Analysis of the Ligand that has been Synthesized

Ligand	Founded %			Calculated %		
	H%	C%	N%	H%	C%	N%
C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄	4.13	58.55	20.31	4.66	58.85	19.06

Conclusions

Liquid and complex structures are determined by molar conductivity, magnetic moments, spectroscopy of the infrared spectrum, element analysis, spectroscopy of the H1-NMR spectrum, mass spectroscopy, and molar elements; octahedral configurations are observed in chromium and iron complexes,

are associated with lost chloride atoms, which are incorporated in the break up (table 5).

Table 5. Fe-L Mass Spectrum's Significant Peaks

No.	Fragmentation	m/z
1	[Fe(L) Cl ₂] ⁺ .Cl	529
2	[Fe(L) Cl ₂] ⁺ .	493
3	[Fe(L) Cl] ⁺ .	458
4	[Fe(L)] ⁺ .	422

Mass Spectra of Ni-L

The peak of the molecular ion (M⁺), base peak, and other significant peaks in the Ni-L spectrum are indicative of lost chloride atoms, which are incorporated in the break up (table 6).

Table 6. Significant Ni-L Mass Spectrum Peaks

No.	Fragmentation	m/z
1	[Ni(L) Cl ₂] ⁺ .	496
2	[Ni(L) Cl] ⁺ .	460
3	[Ni(L)] ⁺ .	425

Analysis of Elemental Composition

The examination of the elements (C.H.N.S) was used to determine the purity of the ligand, and the results are presented in table (7).

while square plainer configurations are observed in nickel complexes.

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